

A Sociological Study on Perceptions of the Role of Education for Career Development Among 12th Grade Students at Ambattur, Chennai.

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the perceptions of 12th-grade students regarding the influence of education on their career development. The findings indicate that although the majority of students regard education as crucial for professional achievement, their perceptions are shaped by parental support, socioeconomic status, career counselling, and practical experience. These insights can help teachers, policymakers, and counsellors vary sure that students' academic goals are in line with their career goals.

Keywords: Education, Career Development, 12th-Grade Students, Career Counselling, Parental Support, Socioeconomic Status.

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Introduction

Education has a big impact on a person's personality, point of view, and career path. Academic credentials are seen as the key to future professional success. The last year of school is very important for 12th graders because they need to make smart choices about college and jobs. Students' views on how education affects career success are influenced by their own goals, their family's expectations, their friends, and their access to career counselling. The goal of this study is to find out how 12th graders see education as a way to help them grow professionally and to give advice to teachers, policymakers, and counsellors.

Objectives of the study

1. To examine the beliefs of 12th-grade students about how important education is for shaping their future careers.
2. To find out if there is a link between what students want to learn and what they want to do for a living.
3. To understand the challenges students facing linking education to career opportunities.
4. To analyse differences in perception shaped by variables including gender, academic performance, and familial background.

Statement of the problem

One of the most important times in a student's life is when they move from school to college or the job market. For 12th graders, school isn't just about getting good grades; it's also about getting ready for their future careers. But many students have trouble making career decisions because they are confused, don't know what to do, or feel pressure from their family or society. Many people think that education is the key to career success, but students don't always know how they feel about its role in shaping their professional future. This gap underscores the necessity to examine students' perceptions of the relationship between education and career advancement.

LITERATURE REVIEW

As noted by “**Paolini (2019), school counsellors guide and support students for college and career readiness**”. **Paolini, A. (2019)**. They play a key role in helping high school students prepare for future academic and professional paths by offering both academic guidance and emotional support. Early exposure to career options, skill development, and mentorship helps students build confidence and feel more prepared for life after school. Additionally, research highlights that parents and community members significantly influence students' aspirations and opportunities. A positive and supportive school environment further enables students to make informed career choices and transition smoothly after graduation.

According to “**The Role of Education for Career Development Among 12th Grade Students**,” **Kumar and Arulmani (2014)** emphasize that education plays a pivotal role in

shaping students' career aspirations by providing them with the knowledge, skills, and exposure needed to make informed decisions. Career guidance programs in schools help bridge the gap between academic learning and real-world career opportunities, especially for students at the senior secondary level.

In the study by “**Rani & Rajalakshmi, 2021**”, “**Education plays a key role in helping students discover their strengths and plan for future careers**”. Career development at the school level is most effective when students are exposed to structured guidance, real-world opportunities, and decision-making support. Research shows that when career education is integrated into the curriculum, students gain clarity about their goals and are better prepared to transition into higher Education.

AREA OF THE STUDY

This study was conducted among 12th-grade students in Ambattur, Chennai to understand how education supports career development. Most students shared that school guidance and subject choices helped them plan their future goals more clearly.

SELECTION OF SAMPLE

The sample for this study consists of 50 students from Ambattur, Chennai, all of whom are my friends and peers. Their responses were collected to understand how their educational experiences have influenced their career development perspectives.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study used a descriptive research method to understand how education supports career development. A structured Google Form with multiple-choice questions was shared among 50 college students in Ambattur, Chennai. The responses were collected through purposive sampling and analysed using Google Sheets to find common patterns and insights.

SOURCES OF DATA

Primary Data: The primary data of this study is the direct responses collected from 50 college students through a Google Form.

Secondary data: The secondary data include articles, reports, and previous research studies related to education and career development.

TOOLS AND TECHNIQUES USED FOR THE STUDY

The main tool used for this study was a Google Form designed with multiple-choice questions to collect responses efficiently. The data was analysed using Google Sheets to identify patterns and draw conclusions related to education and career development.

SCOPE AND LIMITATIONS

This study focuses on understanding how education influences career development among college students in Ambattur, Chennai. It provides insights into students' perceptions based on their academic experiences and future goals. However, the study is limited to a small sample size of 50 students, which may not represent the broader student population. Additionally, since all participants were personally known to the researcher, responses may carry a degree of bias.

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

1. Which group are you studying 12th grade?

Category	No. of Respondents	percent
Science	21	42
Commerce	27	54
Arts	02	4
Total	50	100

Source: Primary data

Most of the people who answered (54 percent of them) are from the Commerce stream, and 42 percent are from the Science stream. This means that students from these two types of schools are more likely to be involved in talks about how their education has affected their job paths.

The Arts stream is only represented by 4 percent of the sample, which shows that few students studying humanities or social studies took part.

The very low number of students in the Arts stream suggests that it is either less popular among students or possibly less promoted within the school environment. This suggests that Commerce is currently the most preferred academic stream among the students in this sample.

2. Do you believe education is important for career development?

Category	No. of Respondents	Percent
Yes	43	86
No	01	2
Not sure	03	6
May be	03	6
total	50	100

Source: Primary data

Most of the students who answered the survey—86 percent—said that education is important for career growth. Only one person (2 percent) said it's not important.

A few students were unsure, with 6 percent choosing “not sure” and another 6 percent saying “maybe.” These answers show that many young people believe education helps them build a better future.

Since the survey was done among college students in Ambattur, their views reflect what students in this area think about how education connects to their career plans.

3. How much do you think your current education will help you in choosing a career?

Category	No. of Respondents	Percent
Very much	30	60
Somewhat	18	36
Very little	01	2
Not at all	01	2
Total	50	100

Source: Primary data

Most of the students who took part in the survey (60 percent) said that their current education will help them a lot in choosing a career. This shows that many of them feel confident that what they are learning now will guide them in making the right decisions for their future.

A good number (36 percent) said their education will help them to some extent, which means they see some connection between their studies and career plans, but not completely.

Only one student (2 percent) felt their education will help very little, and another one (2 percent) said it won't help at all.

These few students might feel that other things like personal interests, skills, or work experience are more important than formal education when it comes to choosing a career

4. Who influences your career decisions the most?

Category	No. of Respondents	percent
Parents/Family	29	58
Teachers/School	1	2
Friends	4	8
Self-interest	16	32
Total	50	100

Source: Primary data

Most students said that their parents or family have the biggest influence on their career decisions. Out of 50 students, 29 chose this option, which makes up 58 per cent of the total. This shows that family plays a strong role in helping students think about their future.

Sixteen students (32 percent) said they make career choices based on their own interests. This means they focus more on what they enjoy or what they want to do.

A few students—4 of them (8 percent)—said their friends influence their decisions. Only one student (2 percent) said teachers or school help them decide.

These answers show that while personal interest matters, most students still look to their family for support and advice when it comes to choosing a career.

5. Do you think guidance and counselling in schools help in career planning?

Category	No. of Respondents	Percent
Yes	21	42
No	9	18
Not sure	18	36
Maybe	2	4
Total	50	100

Source: Primary data

In the survey, 21 students out of 50 said that guidance and counselling in schools help with career planning. This shows that some students feel school support can guide them in thinking about their future.

At the same time, 18 students said they were not sure. This might be because they haven't had enough counselling or don't know how much it can help.

Nine students said it doesn't help, and two said maybe. Some students may not be aware of the counselling services available in their schools.

Others might feel that career decisions depend more on personal interest or family advice than on school guidance.

6. How confident are you that your education will help you get a good job?

Category	No. of Respondents	Percent
Very confident	31	62
Somewhat confident	14	28
Not confident	05	10
Total	50	100

Source: Primary data

To understand how students feel about the link between education and job opportunities, a survey was conducted among 50 college students.

When asked how confident they are that their education will help them get a good job, 31 students (62 percent) said they are very confident.

This shows that most students believe their studies will support their future careers. Fourteen students (28 percent) said they are somewhat confident, meaning they see some value in their education but may still have doubts.

Five students (10 percent) said they are not confident, showing that a few students are unsure about how useful their education will be in finding a good job.

These responses reflect how students view the role of education in shaping their career paths.

7. Which factor do you think is most important for career success?

Category	No of Respondents	Percent
Education	19	38
Skills/Training	29	58
Hard work	2	4
Total	50	100

Source: Primary data

We surveyed 50 college students to find out what they think is most vital for professional success. Training and abilities were most essential to 29 students (58 percent). Many students value hands-on experience and practical skills over class attendance.

Education is a good method to start a profession, according to 19 students (38 percent). No one chose family or friends, and only two participants (4percent) said hard work is vital.

Many students seem to think their education and application will determine their success. Some students may have noted that talented people get jobs faster, which may have influenced their responses.

Some think a degree isn't enough to get a job today. These replies indicate that youngsters are becoming more realistic about the future.

8. Do you plan to continue your studies after 12th grade?

Category	No of Respondents	Percent
Yes, Undergraduate degree	44	88
Yes, Vocational /Skill course	03	6
I want to work immediately	02	4
Not yet decided	01	2
Total	50	100

Source: Primary data

A survey was conducted with 50 college students to learn about their plans after finishing 12th grade. Among them, 44 expressed their desire to pursue an undergraduate degree.

This indicates that a lot of learners are keen on pursuing their studies by taking regular college classes. Three students mentioned that they intend to pursue vocational or skill-based courses, indicating their preference for practical and job-related learning.

Two of them mentioned they're eager to get started immediately, while one is still thinking it over. These answers indicate that pursuing higher education remains the top option for many learners.

Some people might think that having a degree opens up more opportunities for landing a good job. Some people might be interested in picking up skills that can help them make money more quickly.

Overall, the survey indicates that young people are really considering their future and picking paths that align with their aspirations.

9. How relevant do you find the subjects you study now to your future career goals?

Category	No of Respondents	Percent
Very relevant	22	44
Somewhat relevant	07	14
Not very relevant	20	40
Not relevant at all	01	01
Total	50	100

Source: Primary data

A survey was conducted with 50 students to find out how they feel about the subjects they are currently studying. Among them, 22 students expressed that the subjects are super important for their future career aspirations.

This indicates that a lot of learners believe their present schooling is guiding them toward their future goals. Seven students mentioned that the subjects are kind of relevant, indicating they notice a slight connection but don't think it's strong enough.

Twenty students expressed that the subjects don't seem very relevant, indicating that they don't perceive a clear link between what they're studying and the type of jobs they aspire to have in the future. A student mentioned that the subjects aren't relevant whatsoever.

These responses indicate that while some learners feel sure about their education, a lot of them sense a disconnect between their studies and their future career goals. Some people might be learning about topics they didn't pick, particularly if they had few choices.

Others may feel that real job skills are different from what's taught in the classroom. It's obvious that young people are really considering how their learning connects to what lies ahead.

10. What kind of career support do you expect from your school?

Category	No of Respondents	Percent
Career counselling	22	44
Information about courses/colleges	07	14
Internship/Job exposure	20	40
Motivation and guidance from teachers	01	2
Total	50	100

Source: Primary data

To understand what kind of career support for student expect from their school, a survey was conducted with 50 college students. Out of them, 22 students said they want career counselling.

This shows that many students feel the need for proper guidance to help them choose the right path. Twenty students said they expect internship or job exposure, which means they want real-world experience while studying.

Seven students said they want more information about courses and colleges, showing that some students are still exploring their options.

From the collected data, only one student said they expect motivation and guidance from teachers.

These responses indicate that many individuals are seeking practical assistance and straightforward guidance regarding their career planning.

Some might feel a bit confused without the right guidance, while others are eager to build their skills before diving into the workforce.

It's obvious that young people appreciate guidance that assists them in making smart choices about what lies ahead.

Findings

- A majority of students (54 percent) opted for commerce in 12th grade, making it the most popular choice.
- Science was the second most popular choice, with 42 percent of learners picking it, Only 2 people studied arts.
- Most people, about 86 percent, think that education is super important for getting ahead in their careers.
- Only one person mentioned that education isn't important, while a few others were uncertain or responded with "maybe."

- This indicates that a majority view education as an essential element in shaping their future.
- When asked how much their current education helps in picking a career, 60 percent responded with “very much.”
- Another 36 percent said “somewhat,” showing that many students see at least some value in their studies.
- Only two students felt their education helps very little or not at all.
- Parents and family were the biggest influence on career decisions, with 29 students choosing them.
- Sixteen students expressed that their personal interests shape their career decisions, highlighting a trend towards greater independence.
- Just a handful of students mentioned that teachers or friends affect their choices.
- When we asked about career guidance in schools, 21 students responded that it is helpful.
- But 18 students were not sure, and 9 said it doesn’t help, showing mixed opinions.
- Most students (62 percent) feel very confident that their education will help them get a good job.
- Fourteen of the students mentioned that they feel somewhat confident, while five expressed that they do not feel confident at all.
- A total of 29 students identified skills and training as the key factor for achieving career success.
- Nineteen students picked education, proving that formal learning is still important.
- Just two people selected hard work, and nobody went for family or social connections.
- After finishing 12th grade, 44 students are looking to pursue an undergraduate degree, which shows they are really interested in continuing their education.
- Some of the students are interested in pursuing vocational courses or jumping straight into the workforce.
- Concerning how useful their classes are, 22 students said that they were very related to the careers they want to have when asked.
- Twenty students, though, said that the classes weren't very useful, which shows that what they're learning isn't related to their job goals.
- Many students get help with their careers through job counselling or internships that they can do through their schools.

Conclusion

The survey shows that most students value education for their future. Many of them feel that what they are learning now will help them get a good job. At the same time, some students feel that their subjects don’t really match their career goals. A lot of students think skills and training are more useful than just classroom learning. Most students said their family helps them make career decisions, but they also want proper guidance from school. Overall, students are thinking seriously about their future and want support that is practical and helpful,

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